

ROLE OF NAGKESHAR, LODHRA AND TRIPHALA IN MANAGEMENT OF HARMORRODS

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ABSTRACT

Arsha (Haemorrhoids) is a common condition recognised as the most perturbing for its enemy like behaviour. As regards management, Bhesaja, Kshara, Agni & Sastra has been advocated in Ayurveda, while certain conditions don't allow surgical interference as well as application of Kshara & Agni. Keeping the above facts in view, an elaborate research has been carried out with a herbal preparation Nagkeshar, Lodhara and Triphala in the preview of Bhesaja Cikitsa (Medical Management) & the efficacy of the drug seems to be significant.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurvedic lexicons has identified certain diseases as 'Mahagada' keeping in mind the severity & troublesome behavior. One such condition is 'Arsha', which is most common in day to day medicinal as well as surgical practice since the primitive age, possessing problem to both the patient as well as the-clinician.

Its prevalence is steadily increasing with the cultivation of civilization which needs proper attention.

As per available records, chances of piles is more than 40% over the age of 50 years, while half of the adult population in the west.

The definition of 'Arsha' said by Vagbhata is worth to establish the disease being severe in nature when associated with persistent bleeding occurs most likely during and after defecation. There is severe burning and sucking pain apart from secondary anaemia and anal irritation associated with haemorrhoids.

Some times there is prolapse and discharge as an accompanying complication. Prompt attention of the clinician is very often warranted and improper management leads to threatening the life, though not immediate fatal; it is immensely troublesome.

Ayurveda advocates four categories of management like Bhesaja (medicine), Kshara, agni & Sashtra (Surgery) Karma in chronological order.

The present work envisages an intensive trial through medicine (Bhesaja) alone. As most of the cases opt for conservative treatment, as it is more economical, painless, no hospitalization is required and no complication observed during or after medication.

A Strategy of medical management has been formulated and implemented through this endeavor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Out of 4 categories of management described, Bhesaja Chikitsa (medical management) has been planned & exercised through this study with a herbal preparations Nagkeshar, Lodhra and Triphala.

The study carried out on 40 patients of either sex. The diagnosis was confirmed through digital and proctoscopic examinations. Inspection of piles mass has been done and its position, colour, size, number and degree, including signs of inflammation or thrombosis, prolapse of piles etc. has been recorded for the purpose of evaluation.

Drug, Dose & Duration

The drug has been administered in the dose of 5 gms (1 tsf.) twice daily at 12 hrs. interval with lukewarm water for a period of 30 consecutive days.

Evaluation

The evaluation has been carried out at 7 days interval and recorded, which is displayed in respective tables.

Features of 1", 2" and 3" degree piles**I. 1" degree piles**

Hypertrophy of the internal haemorrhoidal plexus remains entirely. within the anal canal presented with the complains of rectal bleeding and discomfort or irritation.

II. 2" degree piles

Here the piles will descend so that they prolapse during defecation but spontaneous reduction takes place afterwards. There may be small skin tag, some. mucous discharge, soreness and irritation.

III. 3% degree piles

Here the pile masses remain prolapsed after defecation and require replacement. These often descend spontaneously or on exercise. The mucosa overlaying such haemorrhoids undergoes squamous metaplasia. It is associated with Mucous discharge, pruritus ani and anaemia.

OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

As regards sex disparity, the male, female ratio is negligible which suggests that any sex is prone to hemorrhoids. However, the prone age group revealed among 20-50 yrs. The reason of higher incidence among this age group may be that this group is the most productive and there is exposure to different food habits favorable to Nidana & Samprapti.

As regards food habits, a higher incidence of 80% was revealed among non vegetarians, which is highly suggestive in lieu of etiological factors responsible for piles.

Sedentary life style invites a favorable condition in the body towards piles which has been reflected being 60% during the course of trial.

On the ground of effectiveness, a declaration has been extended as 60% of very good and 40% of good result after completion of trial for a period of 30 days.

Among 40 number of cases, 36 had bleeding P/R under G1,G2,G3 severity forming 23, 11 & 3 number of cases respectively. There was a considerable decrease in bleeding which steadily improved after 1st week, 2nd week, 3rd week & 4th week evident in table No-2.

As regards pain, among 32 cases there was complete relief from pain which amounts 100% improvement.

Table -2: Showing the severity of different sign and symptoms among the patient before and after treatment with percentage of patients improved.

Sign/ Symptoms	Before Tr			A.T. 1st week		A.T. 2nd week		A.T. 3rd Week		A.T. 4th Week										
	T	G ₁	G ₂	G ₃	%	T	G ₁	G ₂	G ₃	%	T	G ₁	G ₂	G ₃	%					
Bleeding	36	22	11	3	66.66	25	8	3	0	100	30	5	1	0	100	32	3	12	0	100
Pain	36	11	20	5	66.66	6	20	10	0	91.66	18	16	2	0	100	30	6	0	0	100
No. of mass	40	18	14	8	7.5	0	18	14	8	12.5	2	17	13	8	57.5	4	17	12	7	62.5
Size of mass	40	8	22	10	17.5	0	13	20	7	30	0	17	16	5	42.5	2	17	18	3	67.5
Inflammation	24	14	8	2	33.33	5	16	3	0	75	8	14	2	0	95.83	31	3	0	0	95.83
Prolaps	6	0	4	2	66.66	0	2	2	2	66.66	0	4	2	0	93.33	1	4	1	0	83.33
Constipation	38	11	27	0	73.68	7	27	4	0	92.10	18	20	0	0	94.73	29	9	0	0	97.36

% - percentage of the patients improved

G₃ - Severe grade G₂ - Moderate grade G₁ Mild grade G₀ Absence,

T- Total number of patient, A.T. After Treatment

Table - 3: Showing the incidence of different degrees of piles (n=40)

Degrees of Piles	No. of cases	%
1st Degree	30	75
2nd Degree	7	17.5
3rd Degree	3	7.5

Table – 4: Showing the effect of therapy on different degrees of piles.

Signs symptoms	1st Degree N1 = 30				2nd Degree N2 = 7				3rd Degree N3 = 3			
	No. of cases	Complete relief	Reduced	No Change	No. of cases	Complete relief	Reduced	No Change	No. of cases	Complete relief	Reduced	No Change
Bleeding	26	25	1	0	7	5	2	0	3	1	2	0
Pain	28	24	4	0	6	6	1	0	2	2	0	0
Inflammation	16	14	2	0	7	7	0	0	2	0	2	0
Cospitation	28	24	3	1	7	7	0	0	3	1	1	0
Size of piles	30	4	15	11	7	0	4	3	3	0	1	2
Prolapse	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	0	2	1

N_1 = Total no. of patients in 1st Degree Piles

N_2 = Total no. of patients in 2nd Degree Piles

N_3 = Total no. of patients in 3rd Degree Piles

Table – 5: Showing the clinical assessment of the result on 1st, 2nd, 3rd degree piles and on total after completion of Trial duration of 30 days.

Clinical Assessment	1st Degree N1 = 30		2nd Degree N2 = 7		3rd Degree N3 = 3		Total	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Very Good	22	73.33	8	71	2	66.66	24	60
Good	8	26.66	2	29	1	33.33	16	40
Fair	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Poor	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-

f = Frequency (no. of patients) % = percentage

N_1 = no. of patients in 1st Degree, N_2 = no. of patients in 2nd Degree

N_3 = no. of patients in 3rd Degree, Very good = more than 75% improvement in all signs and symptoms, good = 50-75% improvement improvement in all signs and symptoms,

Similarly constipation is an accompanying feature associated to piles usually requires additional support of medicine. During the trial, out of 38 cases suffering from constipation, had a complete improvement recorded among 34 patients having 97.36% recovery.

24 number of cases were found to be having inflamed pile mass during inspection. After completion of 4 weeks of treatment, recovery was ascertained among 22 numbers of cases amounting 95.83%.

Regarding size & number of masses, there was disappearance of the mass & reduction in size amounting an improvement about 62.5% & 67.5% respectively.

The statistical adjudication of cardinal sign and symptoms acknowledged as highly significant at 0.1 % level in case of bleeding with p value less than 0.001. (Table No. 6)

Similarly statistical analysis on pain was recorded as highly significant having p value less than 0.001 (Table No.-7)

No. of masses, a 4 week trial have been ascertained as the p value being less than 0.001 each respectively. (Table No. 8,9, 10)

The clinical assessment has been carried out on different stages like 1st, 2nd & 3rd degree, and the efficacy has been ascertained as a very good response being 73.33 %, 71 % & 66.66 % respectively which amounts a total efficacy of 60%, (Table No- 7) (Fig:-2 and 3)

Similarly good response has been achieved on 1st, 2nd & 3rd degree piles among 26.66 %, 21% & 33.33% respectively which amounts a total efficacy of 40%. (Fig:-2)

Based upon the clinical efficacy and statistical adjudication, the herbal preparation be recommended as a dependable, highly satisfactory and a safe formulation in the treatment of 1st & 2nd degree piles.

In cases where surgery is contraindicated like very old age as well as pregnancy, it can be safely used as a dependable medicine.

Table -6: Statistical analysis showing the effect of the trial drug to bleeding on 1st, 2nd and 3rd degree piles and on totality.

Sign/ Symp.	Degree of piles	Duration of Treat-ment	Mean±S.D.	% of improvement	d.f. (n-1)	t-value	p-value	Remarks	
Bleeding	1st	B.T.	1.42±0.58					Highly significant at 0.1% level of significance	
		A.T ₁	0.73 ±0.53	21.62		6.88	<0.001		
		A.T ₂	0.30 ±0.55	51.35	25	10.68	<0.001		-do-
		A.T ₃	0.08 ±0.27	94.59		4.05	<0.001		-do-
		A.T ₄	0.04 ±0.20	97.29		14.45	<0.001		-do-
	2nd	B.T.	1.71 ±0.75						
		A.T ₁	1.01 ±0.71	41.67		0.98	<0.05	Signi. at 5% level of significance	
		A.T ₂	0.71 ±1.0	58.33	2	1.88	<0.001	highly significant	
		A.T ₃	0.28 ±0.49	83.33		3.96	<0.001	0.11% level	
		A.T ₄	0.28 ±0.49	83.33		3.96	<0.001	-do-	
	3rd	B.T.	2.0 ±1.0						
		A.T ₁	1.65 ±1.15	16.67		0.98	>0.05	In significant at 5% level of significance	
		A.T ₂	1.0 ±1.0	50.06	35	1.88	>0.05	-do-	
		A.T ₃	0.33 ±0.58	83.33		3.96	>0.05	-do-	
		A.T ₄	0.33 ±0.58	83.33		3.96	>0.05	-do-	
	Total	B.T.	1.5 ±0.64						
		A.T ₁	0.86 ±0.72	43.64		7.81	<0.001	Highly significant at 0.1% level of significance	
		A.T ₂	0.42 ±0.64	72.73		12.40	<0.001	-do-	
		A.T ₃	0.14 ±0.34	90.91		17.02	<0.001	-do-	
		A.T ₄	0.11 ±0.31	92.73		17.04	<0.001	-do-	

A.T₁-After complete of 1st week of treatment, A.T₂-After complete of 2nd week of treatment
 A.T₃-After complete of 3rd week of treatment, A.T₄-After complete of 4th week of treatment,
 < = less than, > Greater than, d.f. = degree of freedom, n= total number of patient, S.D. = standard deviation.

Table -7: Showing the effect of the trial drug to pain on 1st, 2nd and 3rd degree piles and on totality.

Sign/ Symp.	Degree of piles	Duration of Treat-ment	Mean±S.D.	% of improvement	d.f. (n-1)	t-value	p-value	Remarks	
Pain	1st	B.T.	1.82 ±0.61					Highly significant at 0.1% level of significance	
		A.T ₁	1.14 ±0.68	37.25		7.54	<0.001		
		A.T ₂	0.57± 0.57	68.62	27	1.40	<0.001		-do-
		A.T ₃	0.14 ±0.36	92.15		14.57	<0.001		-do-
		A.T ₄	0.14 ±0.36	92.15		14.57	<0.001		-do-
	2nd	B.T.	1.83 ±0.75						
		A.T ₁	1.17 ±0.75	36.66		3.14	<0.05	Signi. at 5% level of significance	

		A.T ₂	0.50 ±0.84	72.73	5	6.24	<0.01	significant at 1% level of significant	
		A.T ₃	0.17 ±0.41	90.91			7.84	<0.001	Highly significant at 0.1% level
		A.T ₄	0.17 ±0.41	90.91			7.84	<0.001	-do-
	3rd	B.T.	1.0 ±0.00						
		A.T ₁	1.0 ±0.00	0					As there are two cases result may be assessed clinically
		A.T ₂	1.0 ±0.00	0	1				
		A.T ₃	0	0					
		A.T ₄	0	100					
	Total	B.T.	1.83 ±0.65						
		A.T ₁	1.11 ±0.67	39.99			8.37	<0.001	Highly significant at 0.1% level of significance
		A.T ₂	0.55 ±0.61	69.70	35		12.67	<0.001	-do-
		A.T ₃	0.17 ±0.34	90.91			15.90	<0.001	-do-
		A.T ₄	0.11 ±0.32	93.94			15.90	<0.001	-do-

Table -8: Statistical analysis showing the trial drug to Inflammation on 1st, 2nd and 3rd degree piles and on totality.

Sign/ Symp.	Degree of piles	Duration of Treatment	Mean±S.D.	% of improvement	d.f. (n-1)	t-value	p-value	Remarks	
Inflama-tion	1st	B.T.	1.37± 0.50					Significant at 0.1% level of significance	
		A.T ₁	1.0± 0.63	27.22		2.96	<0.01		
		A.T ₂	0.56± 0.51	54.54	27	6.0	<0.001	Highly significant at 0.0% level	
		A.T ₃	0.18 ±0.40	86.36		11.8	<0.001	-do-	
		A.T ₄	0.12 ±0.34	90.90		11.11	<0.001	-do-	
	2nd	B.T.	1.28 ±0.49						
		A.T ₁	1.0 ±0.0	22.22		1.50	>0.05	Insignificant	
		A.T ₂	0.28± 0.49	44.44	5	4.55	<0.01	significant	
		A.T ₃	0	100		8.24	<0.001	Highly significant	
	3rd	A.T ₄	0	100		8.24	<0.001	-do-	
		B.T.	2.0 ±0.0						
		A.T ₁	1.50 ±0.70	25		1.01		Clinical assessment may be made instead of significant test	
		A.T ₂	1.50 ±0.70	25	1	1.01			
		A.T ₃	1.0 ±1.41	56		1.00			
	Total	A.T ₄	0.50 ±0.70	75		1.24			
		B.T.	1.37 ±0.49						
		A.T ₁	1.04 ±0.55	24.24		3.36	<0.001	Highly significant	
		A.T ₂	0.54 ±0.59	60.60	23	7.37	<0.001	-do-	
		A.T ₃	0.20 ±0.51	84.84		11.92	<0.001	-do-	
		A.T ₄	0.12 ±0.33	90.90		13.89	<0.001	-do-	

Table -9: Statistical analysis showing the effect of the trial drug to Constipation on 1st, 2nd and 3rd degree piles and on totality.

Sign/ Symp.	Degree of piles	Duration of Treat-ment	Mean±S.D.	% of improvement	d.f. (n-1)	t-value	p-value	Remarks	
CONSTI- PATION	1st	B.T.	1.75 ±0.44					Highly significant	
		A.T ₁	0.96 ±0.51	44.90		9.83	<0.001	-do-	
		A.T ₂	0.53 ±0.51	69.39	27	10.23	<0.001	-do-	
		A.T ₃	0.25 ±0.44	85.71		13.32	<0.001	-do-	
		A.T ₄	0.14 ±0.34	91.83		14.57	<0.001	-do-	
	2nd	B.T.	1.79 ±0.49						
		A.T ₁	0.71 ±0.49	33.33		3.24	<0.05	Significant	
		A.T ₂	0.43 ±0.53	75.00	6	4.54	<0.01	Significant	
		A.T ₃	0.14 ±0.38	91.66		7.82	<0.001	Highly significant	
		A.T ₄	0.0 ±0.0	100.00		9.21	<0.001	-do-	
	3rd	B.T.	1.50 ±0.71						
		A.T ₁	1.33 ±0.58	33.33		0.98	>0.05	In significant	
		A.T ₂	0.67 ±0.58	75.0	2	-	>0.05	-do-	
		A.T ₃	0.33 ±0.58	91.66		3.97	>0.05	Significant	
		A.T ₄	0.0 ±0.0	100		4.98	<0.001	Highly significant	
	Total	B.T.	1.71 ±0.46						
		A.T ₁	0.92 ±0.54	46.15		9.55	<0.001	Highly significant	
		A.T ₂	0.55 ±0.50	67.69	37	13.11	<0.001	-do-	
		A.T ₃	0.24 ±0.43	86.15		16.72	<0.001	-do-	
		A.T ₄	0.10 ±0.31	93.84		17.58	<0.001	-do-	

Table -10: Statistical analysis showing the effect of the trial drug to No. of Masses on 1st, 2nd and 3rd degree piles and on totality.

Sign/ Symp.	Degree of piles	Duration of Treat-ment	Mean±S.D.	% of improvement	d.f. (n-1)	t-value	p-value	Remarks	
No. of Masses	1st	B.T.	1.63± 0.76					Insignificant	
		A.T ₁	1.53 ±0.80	6.12		1.82	>0.05		
		A.T ₂	1.50 ±0.86	8.16	29	2.04	>0.05	Insignificant	
		A.T ₃	1.10 ±0.88	32.65		6.56	<0.001	Highly significant	
		A.T ₄	0.93 ±0.87	42.85		8.15	<0.001	Highly significant	
	2nd	B.T.	2.0 ±0.82						
		A.T ₁	2.0 ±0.82	0		No chance	-	No Change	
		A.T ₂	2.0 ±0.82	0	6	No chance	-	No Change	
		A.T ₃	1.28 ±1.11	35.71		2.08	>0.05	Insignificant	
		A.T ₄	1.28 ±1.11	35.71		2.08	>0.05	Insignificant	
	3rd	B.T.	2.0 ±1.0						
		A.T ₁	2.0 ±1.0	0		0		No Change	

		A.T ₂	2.0 \pm 1.0	0	2	0		No Change
		A.T ₃	2.0 \pm 1.0	0		0		No Change
		A.T ₄	2.0 \pm 1.0	0		0		No Change
	Total	B.T.	1.95 \pm 1.64					
		A.T ₁	1.65 \pm 0.88	15.38		1.82	>0.05	Insignificant
		A.T ₂	0.62 \pm 0.92	16.66	39	2.30	<0.05	Significant
		A.T ₃	1.12 \pm 0.96	34.74		7.43	<0.001	Highly significant
		A.T ₄	1.07 \pm 0.94	44.87		9.00	<0.001	Highly significant

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